

PREPARATION OF ANTIBACTERIALS FROM ORGANO-MERCURIALS.
PART III. MERCURATED AMINES

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Several mercurated amines, some of which were prepared by others but whose bactericidal properties not investigated before, have been prepared and their bactericidal properties investigated.

The present work deals with some simple mercurated amines, which have been prepared by other workers, but the bactericidal action of which has not been tested. A list of the compounds, which includes a few not previously described, together with their m.p.'s and their analyses is given in Table III. A summary of their bacteriological activities is given in Tables I and II. It will be noticed that some of the compounds are highly active *in vitro*.

There are some points of interest in the behaviour of the compounds. For example, compounds Nos. 12, 16, 21 and 22, which were prepared by using HgCl_2 instead of mercuric acetate, gave on analysis compositions corresponding to the hydrochlorides of the chloromercuri compounds, or in other words, they contained one mol. of HCl extra, which was obviously combined with the free primary NH_2 groups. Secondly, whereas most of the compounds dissolved easily in dilute HCl , and could be diazotised, compounds Nos., 1, 5, 8, 9, 11, 17, 18, 19, 20, 25, 26, 27 and 28 gave on treatment with dilute HCl sparingly soluble chloromercuri compounds which were difficult to diazotise. Better results were obtained by diazotising the original acetoxy compounds in dilute acetic acid solution. Thirdly, a few of the compounds (Nos., 17, 18, 20, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27 & 28) were found to dissolve in dilute NaOH solution, due to the conversion of the acetoxymercuri group into the hydroxymercuri group, the resulting compounds being soluble in water and strongly alkaline in reaction. The same behaviour is described in connection with the *p*-hydroxymercuri derivative of ethylaniline (cf. Newton Friend, "Text Book of Inorganic Chemistry", Vol. XI, Part II, p. 123).

The mercury in the products was analysed by the gold crucible method as described in previous parts (Guha Sircar *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 357, 535) and the bactericidal activity by the Rideal-Walker drop test method, using a 24 hour culture of *E. Coli* as the test organism. The p_{H} of the medium was kept between 6.5 and 7.5. The temperature was 28.5° .

TABLE I

Serial No.	Name of the derivatives.	After x minutes.	Maximum effective dilution.
3.	<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminophenylmercuri acetate.	12½ mins.	1 : 100,000
4.	<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminophenylmercuri chloride	"	1 : 10,000
5.	<i>p</i> -Ethylaminophenylmercuri chloride	"	1 : 10,000
7.	5-Acetoxymercuri- <i>o</i> -toluidine	"	1 : 10,000
9.	Diacetoxymercuri- <i>m</i> -toluidine	"	1 : 10,000
10.	Acetoxymercuri- <i>p</i> -toluidine	"	1 : 10,000
11.	Chloromercuri- <i>p</i> -toluidine	3 hrs.	1 : 200,000
"	" " "	24 "	1 : 400,000
12.	Chloromercuri- <i>p</i> -toluidine hydrochloride (?)	12¼ mins.	1 : 200,000
"	" " "	1½ hr.	1 : 400,000
"	" " "	3 "	1 : 400,000

TABLE I (contd.)

Serial No.	Name of the derivative.	After x minutes.	Maximum effective dilution.
13.	<i>p</i> -Acetoxymercuri- <i>o</i> -nitraniline	12½ mins.	1 : 2000
14.	3(?)-Acetoxymercuribenzidine (+1 mol. of benzidine)	"	1 : 1000
15.	Acetoxymercuri- <i>p</i> -chloroaniline	"	1 : 100,000
16.	Chloromercuri- <i>p</i> -chloroaniline hydrochloride (?)	"	1 : 125,000
17.	Acetoxymercuri- <i>o</i> -anisidine [+1 mol. of Hg(OAc) ₂]	"	1 : 10,000
18.	Chloromercuri- <i>o</i> -anisidine	"	1 : 10,000
20.	Chloromercuri- <i>p</i> -anisidine	"	1 : 10,000
21.	Chloromercuri- <i>o</i> -anisidine hydrochloride (?)	"	1 : 125,000
22.	Chloromercuri- <i>p</i> -anisidine hydrochloride (?)	"	1 : 100,000
	" " "	1 hr.	1 : 200,000
	" " "	3 "	1 : 200,000
23.	Dichloromercuripyridine hydrochloride	12½ mins.	1 : 100,000
24.	Dichloromercuriquinoline hydrochloride	"	1 : 10,000
25.	Acetoxymercurimethyl anthranilate	"	1 : 10,000
26.	Chloromercurimethyl anthranilate	"	1 : 1000
27.	Acetoxymercuriethyl anthranilate	"	1 : 1000
28.	Chloromercuriethyl anthranilate	"	1 : 1000
29.	Diacetoxymercurinaphthylamine	"	1 : 100,000

TABLE II

Bactericidal action of chloromercuri-p-teluidine considering the time and dilution factors simultaneously.

Dilution.	10mins.	20mins.	30mins.	40mins.	50mins.	60mins.	70mins.	80mins.	90mins.	100mins.	120mins.	180mins.
1 : 10,000												
1 : 20,000												
1 : 30,000												
1 : 40,000	—											
1 : 50,000	+											
1 : 60,000												
1 : 70,000	..	—										
1 : 80,000	..	+										
1 : 90,000												
1 : 100,000	..	..	—									
1 : 110,000	..	..	+									
1 : 120,000	..	..	..	—								
1 : 130,000	..	..	..	+								
1 : 140,000												
1 : 150,000	..	..	..	..	—							
1 : 160,000	..	..	..	..	+							
1 : 170,000	..	..	..	..	..	—						
1 : 180,000	..	..	..	..	..	+						
1 : 190,000	..	..	..	..	..	..	—					
1 : 200,000	..	..	..	..	..	..	+	—				
1 : 210,000	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	+				
1 : 220,000	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	—			
1 : 230,000	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	+			
1 : 240,000	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	—	—	
1 : 250,000	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	+	+	
1 : 300,000	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	—
1 : 310,000	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	+

(—indicates inhibition of growth and + indicates growth not checked).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Most of the compounds were prepared according to methods described by N. Fried (loc. cit.). Compounds Nos. 17, 18, 20, 21, 22, 24, 26, 27 and 28 were prepared *new* by very similar methods. For the new compounds 12, 16, 21 and 22, HgCl₂ was used instead of mercuric acetate, and the HCl adducts of the chloromercuri derivatives were obtained as shown by analysis. Compounds Nos. 1, 5, 8, 9, 11, 17, 18, 19, 20, 25, 26, 27 and 28 are apparently insoluble in dilute HCl and compounds 17, 18, 20, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27 and 28 are apparently soluble in alkalis, due to reasons mentioned in the introduction.

As the work was carried out in 1946 at Dacca, in the midst of occasional interruptions, all the members of a particular series like the nitro and naphthyl derivatives could not be studied. The names, melting points and the analytical data of the compounds are given in Table III.

TABLE III.

No.	Name of derivatives.	M.p.	Hg		Chlorine	
			Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.
1.	<i>p</i> -Aminophenylmercuri acetate	166-67°	56.98%	56.35%	—	—
2.	<i>p</i> -Aminophenylmercuri chloride	188-89°	61.06	62.24	10.84%	11.00%
3.	<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminophenylmercuri acetate	164°	52.77	52.35	—	—
4.	<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminophenylmercuri chloride	223°	56.26	54.92	9.96	10.30
5.	<i>p</i> -Ethylaminophenylmercuri acetate	129-30°	52.77	51.11	—	—
6.	<i>p</i> -Ethylaminophenylmercuri chloride	141-43°	56.26	55.91	9.96	9.56
7.	5-Acetoxymercuri- <i>o</i> -toluidine	144°	54.79	54.69	—	—
8.	5-Chloromercuri- <i>o</i> -toluidine	175-76°	58.56	57.95	10.40	10.16
9.	Diacetoxymercuri- <i>m</i> -toluidine	191°	64.21	63.14	—	—
10.	Acetoxymercuri- <i>p</i> -toluidine	182-84°	54.79	54.44	—	—
11.	Chloromercuri- <i>p</i> -toluidine	170°	58.56	57.89	10.40	10.26
12.	Chloromercuri- <i>p</i> -toluidine hydrochloride	163°	52.9	52.38	18.73	19.23
13.	<i>p</i> -Acetoxymercuri- <i>o</i> -nitroaniline	Above 260°	50.51	51.05	—	—
14.	3 (?) -Acetoxymercuri benzidine + 1 mol. of benzidine	138-40°	31.95	31.79	—	—
15.	Acetoxymercuri- <i>p</i> -chloroaniline	207-9°	51.87	52.47	9.50	9.31
16.	Chloromercuri- <i>p</i> -chloroaniline hydrochloride	158°	50.19	50.95	28.73	28.96
17.	Acetoxymercuri- <i>o</i> -anisidine + 1 mol. of mercuric acetate	190-92°	57.23	58.78	—	—
18.	Chloromercuri- <i>o</i> -anisidine	170-73°	55.86	56.89	9.91	10.22
19.	Acetoxymercuri- <i>p</i> -anisidine + 1 mol. of mercuric acetate	145°	57.23	58.59	—	—
20.	Chloromercuri- <i>p</i> -anisidine	158-60°	55.86	55.26	9.91	9.74
21.	Chloromercuri- <i>o</i> -anisidine hydrochloride	174-78°	50.76	48.57	18.02*	17.32
22.	Chloromercuri- <i>p</i> -anisidine hydrochloride	148-52°	50.76	50.08	18.02	17.30
23.	Dichloromercuripyridine hydrochloride	198°	68.44	69.29	18.22	19.16
24.	Dichloromercuriquinoline hydrochloride	Above 198°	63.05	64.00	16.78	17.05
25.	Acetoxymercurimethyl anthranilate	178-80°	48.9	47.74	—	—
26.	Chloromercurimethyl anthranilate	186°	51.87	52.37	9.50	9.30
27.	Acetoxymercuriethyl anthranilate	168-69°	47.29	48.55	—	—
28.	Chloromercuriethyl anthranilate	184°	50.06	49.32	8.86	8.78
29.	2 : 4 Diacetoxymercuri- <i>o</i> -naphthylamine	Indef.	60.70	59.71	—	—